

Studies in the Indole Field. Part VI. Synthesis of Some Nitro- and Amino-indoles

S. P. Hiremath and S. Siddappa

4-Nitro-7-methylindole, 5-nitro-7-methylindole, 5-methyl-7-nitroindole, and 5-methoxy-7-nitroindole have been synthesised by the Fischer method, using polyphosphoric acid as the cyclising agent. A few amino-indoles, which are of interest as antiserotonin agents, have been prepared by reduction of the corresponding nitroindoles with Raney nickel and hydrogen and characterised by preparation of their picrates and benzoyl derivatives.

The synthesis of a nitroindole was first reported by Majima and Kotake¹ who synthesised 6-nitroindole through nitration of ethyl indole-3-carboxylate. Later Hughes *et al.*² reported the synthesis of 7-nitroindole. Rydon and Siddappa³ on repeating their work did not find it to be 7-nitroindole. Rydon and Siddappa³ attempted the Fischer cyclisation of *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazones of ethyl pyruvate under a variety of conditions, but the compounds could not be cyclised, probably due to the deactivating influence of the nitro group. The use of polyphosphoric acid as a cyclising agent, however, lead to the synthesis of 7-nitroindole⁴ and later all the four nitroindoles were similarly synthesised⁵.

The nitroindoles and nitrotryptophans⁶ would be of interest as bacterial inhibitors. Nitroindoles containing another substituent on the benzenoid ring, such as methyl or methoxyl, would be of further interest for a study of the influence of substituents on bacterial inhibition and for preparation of the corresponding tryptophans, tryptamines, and other derivatives of biological interest. In the present communication, syntheses of some nitroindoles with methyl or methoxyl substituents on the benzenoid ring and the corresponding aminoindoles are described.

Ethyl pyruvate 2-methyl-5-nitrophenylhydrazone (IIa) was prepared from 2-methyl-5-nitrobenzenediazonium chloride (Ia) by the Japp-Klingemann reaction with ethyl methylacetoacetate and cyclised with polyphosphoric acid to ethyl 4-nitro-7-methylindole-2-carboxylate (IIIa). The latter was saponified to the acid (IVa). 4-Nitro-7-methylindole (Va) was finally obtained by decarboxylation of (IVa) by heating it with quinoline and cupric oxide.

By a similar sequence of reactions 2-methyl-4-nitroaniline, 2-nitro-4-methylaniline, and 2-nitro-4-methoxyaniline were converted into 5-nitro-7-methylindole (Vb), 5-methyl-7-

1. *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2237.
2. *Proc. Roy. Soc., N. S. Wales*, 1930, 72, 209.
3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2462.
4. Singer and Shive, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 84.
5. Parmeter *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 4621.
6. Hiremath and Siddappa, *J. Karnatak Univ.*, 1961, 8, 1.

Similarly the nitrophenylhydrazones (IIb, IIc, and IIId) were prepared from the respective anilines. The compounds with their physical characteristics and analytical data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Substituents.	*Cryst. shape.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
IIa	2-Methyl- 5-nitro-	Golden yellow needles	130°	63	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃	C : 54.45% H : 5.67 N : 16.00	54.33% 5.70 15.84
IIb	2-Methyl- 4-nitro-	Yellow prisms	150°	60	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃	C : 54.51 H : 6.17 N : 16.03	54.33 5.70 15.84
IIc	2-Nitro- 4-methyl-	Yellow needles	148°	68	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃	C : 54.45 H : 6.17 N : 15.50	54.33 5.70 15.84
IIId	2-Nitro- 4-methoxy-	Orange needles	140°	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₃	C : 51.37 H : 5.35 N : 15.20	51.23 5.37 14.94

*All the compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

Ethyl 4-Nitro-7-methylindole-2-carboxylate (IIIa).—The preceding hydrazone (IIa) (10 g.) was added in small portions to polyphosphoric acid (prepared from 50 g. of P₂O₅ and 30 ml H₃PO₄), heated to 80°. The mixture was vigorously stirred whereby the temperature spontaneously rose to 95°, which was then maintained at 95-100° for 15 min. and cooled to the room temperature. Ice-water was then added to decompose the polyphosphoric acid when ethyl 4-nitro-7-methylindole-2-carboxylate separated as a yellow solid. It was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

The ethyl indole-2-carboxylates (IIIb-d) were prepared similarly from the corresponding phenylhydrazones. In the preparation of (IIIb) and (IIIc), the polyphosphoric acid was initially heated to 70° and cyclised at 80-90° for 15 min. In the case of (IIId), cyclisation was complete in 10 min. The compounds with their physical characteristics and analytical data are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Substituents.	*Cryst. shape.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
IIIa	4-Nitro- 7-methyl-	Pale yellow needles	200°	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂	C : 57.90% H : 5.24 N : 11.42	58.05 4.87 11.29
IIIb	5-Nitro- 7-methyl-	Shining yellow needles	210-11°	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂	C : 58.43 H : 5.35 N : 11.13	58.05 4.87 11.29
IIIc	5-Methyl- 7-nitro	Pale yellow needles	115°	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂	C : 58.16 H : 5.40 N : 11.58	58.05 4.87 11.29
IIId	5-Methoxy- 7-nitro-	Orange needles	110°	74	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₅ N ₂	C : 54.05 H : 4.52 N : 10.45	54.55 4.56 10.60

*All the compounds were crystallised from aq. ethanol.

4-Nitro-7-methylindole-2-carboxylic Acid (IVa).—To a solution of ethyl 4-nitroindole-2-carboxylate (6 g.) in hot ethanol (100 ml) was added a solution of KOH (5 g.) in water (10 ml) and the mixture kept at the room temperature for 6 hr. when a copious precipitate of the potassium salt separated. Warm water (200 ml) formed a clear solution, which was added slowly with stirring to excess HCl. The solid was collected, washed with water, dried, and crystallised from ethanol.

The indole-2-carboxylic acids (IV b-d) were similarly prepared from the corresponding esters (III b-d) (Table III).

TABLE III

No.	Substituents.	*Cryst. shape.	†M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
IVa	4-Nitro- 7-methyl-	Yellow tiny needles	305-306°	04	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂	C : 54.50 H : 3.61 N : 12.90	54.54 3.66 12.73
IVb	5-Nitro- 7-methyl-	Yellow needles	> 320°	90	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂	C : 54.75 H : 4.20 N : 13.01	54.54 3.66 12.73
IVc	5-Methyl- 7-nitro-	Yellow needles	270-71°	04	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂	C : 54.83 H : 4.05 N : 12.51	54.54 3.66 12.73
IVd	5-Methoxy- 7-nitro-	Orange needles	262-63°	84	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₅ N ₂	C : 50.98 H : 3.44 N : 12.20	50.84 3.41 11.87

*All the compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

†With decomposition.

4-Nitro-7-methylindole (Va).—A mixture of 4-nitro-7-methylindole-2-carboxylic acid (4 g.), cupric oxide (0.5 g.), and freshly distilled quinoline (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 2 hr. The dark mixture, after cooling to the room temperature, was poured into crushed ice (200 g.) containing HCl (conc., 60ml). After keeping for sometime, the clear solution was filtered and washed with ether. The filtrate was repeatedly extracted with ether and the combined ethereal solution was washed with 10% solution of sodium bicarbonate, followed by water. It was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the solvent removed whereby 4-nitro-7-methylindole was obtained as a yellow crystalline mass. It was recrystallised from ethanol.

The nitroindole-2-carboxylic acids (IV b-d) were decarboxylated as described for the preparation of (Va). The nitroindoles (V a-d) are described in Table IV.

4-Amino-7-methylindole (VIa).—4-Nitro-7-methylindole (1 g.) was reduced in methanol (50 ml) with freshly prepared Raney nickel (0.5 g.) and hydrogen (60 p.s.i.) in a Parr low-pressure hydrogenation apparatus. Disappearance of the yellow colour (ca. 4 hr.) indicated complete reduction of the nitro group. The Raney nickel was removed by filtration and the product washed repeatedly with hot methanol. The combined extracts were decolorised with norit and the methanol removed under reduced pressure whereby the amine separated as a white solid. This amine was found to change colour after sometime; hence it was immediately converted into the picrate and the benzoyl derivative.

The nitroindoles (V b-d) were reduced to the corresponding aminoindoles, as described for (VIa). The aminoindoles (VIa-d) with their derivatives are described in Table V.

TABLE IV

No.	Indoles.	*Cryst. shape.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
Va	4-Nitro- 7-methyl-	Yellow flakes	182°	62	$C_9H_8O_2N_2$	C : 61.09 H : 4.59 N : 15.67	61.35 4.58 15.91
Vb	5-Nitro- 7-methyl-	Golden yellow needles	220°	56	$C_9H_8O_2N_2$	C : 61.72 H : 5.11 N : 15.65	61.35 4.58 15.91
Vc	5-Methyl- 7-nitro-	Yellow needles	130°	66	$C_9H_8O_2N_2$	C : 60.91 H : 5.01 N : 16.13	61.35 4.58 15.91
Vd	5-Methoxy- 7-nitro-	Orange needles	135°	61	$C_9H_8O_3N_2$	C : 56.69 H : 4.58 N : 14.45	56.24 4.20 14.58

*All the compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE V

No.	Substituent	Indoles.			Cryst. shape.	*Benzoyl derivative.			Reqd.
		M.P.	%Yield.	Picrate m.p.		M.P.	Formula.	*Found.	
VIa	4-Amino- 7-methyl-	140-41°	72	203-205°	Colorless tiny needles	195-90°	$C_{16}H_{14}ON_2$	C : 76.98 H : 5.78 N : 11.43	76.79 5.64 11.20
VIb	5-Amino- 7-methyl-	Semi- solid	78	192-93°	Colorless long needles	185°	$C_{16}H_{14}ON_2$	C : 76.93 H : 6.01 N : 11.35	76.79 5.64 11.20
VIc	5-Methyl- 7-amino-	„	72	180-81°	Colorless tiny needles	197-98°	$C_{16}H_{14}ON_2$	C : 76.65 H : 5.89 N : 11.20	76.79 5.64 11.20
VIId	5-Methoxy- 7-amino-	„	73	185-86°	Light grey- ish needles	210°	$C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2$	C : 72.61 H : 5.71 N : 10.65	72.16 5.30 10.52

*All the benzoyl derivatives were crystallised from aqueous ethanol.

The authors wish to express their thanks to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the award of a fellowship to one of them (S.P.H.) and to Shri V. A. Desai for the microanalyses.